

X-Ray Spectral Investigation of Silicon-Ligand Bond in $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$, $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4$ and $(\text{OH})_2\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ Compounds

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X-Ray photoelectron and X-ray emission spectra ($\text{SiK}_{\alpha 1,2}$ and $\text{SiK}_{\beta 1,3}$) of the titled silicon compounds are studied. These spectra reveal only σ -bonding in case of $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$ between silicon and ligand, but in case of $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4$ and $(\text{OH})_2\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$, both σ - and π -bonding have been exhibited. The observation is discussed in terms of simple molecular orbital theory. The SiK_{β} emission spectrum of $(\text{OH})_2\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ shows that the compound suffers a decomposition due to heat produced during X-ray bombardment.

A study of metal $K_{\beta 1,3}$ X-ray emission spectra of organometallic complexes¹⁻⁵, has given a reasonable picture of the involvement of metal $3p$ character in bonds to the ligands. This is because $K_{\beta 1,3}$ emission results from the electronic transition $3p \rightarrow 1s$ will give rise to a fine structure of $K_{\beta 1,3}$ peak with intensities that reflect the amount of $3p$ character in each molecular orbital. It has been shown^{3,4} that if extensive π -bonding is present in the ligand (as in acetylacetonate and tropolonate) then two intense peaks are found in the metal $K_{\beta 1,3}$ emission (these two peaks were associated with σ - and π -character), whereas if no π -bonding is available in the ligand (e.g. silicon oxide) then only one peak is observed, which in turn is associated with σ -character.

In this study, we have chosen some silicon compounds of extensive π -bonding ligand (e.g. phenyl ring) and of no π -bonding ligand (e.g. ethoxide group) mainly to follow the generalisation of this conclusion, by means of X-ray photoelectron and X-ray emission spectroscopy.

Results and Discussion

$\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$:

The silicon $K_{\beta 1,3}$ - K_{β} ' emission spectrum is lined up with

Fig 1 X-Ray spectra of liquid $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$.

its XP valence band spectrum using silicon $2p$ ionisation energy $\text{Si } 2p = 102 \text{ eV}$ and $\text{SiK}_{\alpha 1,2} = 1740 \text{ eV}$, as shown in Fig. 1. The $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$ has a tetrahedral structure, determined by analogy with that of $\text{Si}(\text{OCH}_3)_4$.

The oxygen atoms surrounding the silicon atom will present $2p$ orbitals to the central silicon atom and oriented along the Si-O bond; these orbitals belong to irreducible representations (i.r.) a_1 and t_2 . Interaction of silicon $3p$ orbitals (which also transform as t_2) with the above oxygen

Fig. 2 X-Ray spectra of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{Si}$.

$2p$ orbitals of the same i.r., will give rise to $2t_2$ σ -molecular orbitals (triply degenerate) with considerable amount of Si $3p$ character. The oxygen $2s$ orbitals also transform as a_1 and t_2 , and interaction between Si $3p$ orbitals and oxygen $2s$ orbitals of the same i.r. will give rise to $1t_2$ σ -molecular orbitals but with very much less of Si $3p$ contribution⁷. This is because the oxygen $2s$ orbitals are more tightly bound than oxygen $2p$ orbitals.

Electronic transitions from these two σ -molecular orbitals to a vacancy in silicon $1s$ orbital give rise to two peaks (A and B) in SiK_{β} emission, separated by about 14 eV. Peak B is known as low energy satellite (K_{β}').

$\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4$:

The silicon $K_{\beta 1,3}$ - K_{β} ' X-ray emission spectrum, in line with xp valence band is shown in Fig. 2. The SiK_{β} peak B, in line with xp carbon $2s$ peak, can be associated with $1t_2$

σ -molecular orbital mostly carbon $2s$ in character; this is the energy low satellite, which is characteristic of the energy of the s level in the valence shell of the surrounding⁸.

The energy separation (Δ) between the low energy satellite and the main SiK_{β} peak is associated with energy distance between s and p levels of the surrounding atoms, i.e. $\Delta(\text{SiO}_2) = 14 \sim 15$ eV and $\Delta(\text{SiC}) = 9 \sim 10$ eV. Such energy separation can be used as a guide to the characterisation of the σ -bonding in the main $\text{K}_{\beta 1,3}$ emission. This is because π -bonding should not have an associated satellite, as that would require an out-of-plane p overlap with spherically symmetrical in-plane s orbital.

Fig. 3. SiK_{β} for $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Si}(\text{OH})_2$: (—) with cooling and (---) without cooling.

The low energy satellite is separated from SiK_{β} peak (A) by 10 eV, which in turn can be assigned to silicon $3p$ character in $2i_2$ σ -molecular orbitals. The $\text{Si } 3p$ orbitals can interact with π -orbitals from the phenyl ligand, so that the unresolved tail (C) may be regarded as due to $\text{Si-C } \pi$ -bonding.

In a study of this compound, it is found that the compound suffers a decomposition due to heat produced during X-rays bombardment. To overcome this problem, a cryostat unit with which the sample temperature can be measured and controlled, was employed and the result with and without using the cryostat unit is shown in Fig. 3. Since the silicon is bonded to two types of ligands, therefore two low energy satellite B and B', in line with xp oxygen and carbon $2s$ orbitals, have been reflected in the SiK_{β} spectrum as shown in Fig. 4. The SiK_{β} peak (A) separated from the low energy satellite (B) by about 15 eV, can be assigned to $\text{Si-O } \sigma$ -bonding, and the broad SiK_{β} peak (A') separated from the low energy satellite (B') by about 10 eV, can be related to $\text{Si-C } \sigma$ - and π -bonding.

Conclusion :

The $\text{SiK}_{\beta 1,3}-\text{K}_{\beta}'$ X-ray emission spectrum can be used to study the bonding role played by $\text{Si } 3p$ orbitals in silicon

compounds. In particular, it is possible, by using the $\text{K}_{\beta}'-\text{K}_{\beta 1,3}$ energy separation (Δ) established for compounds in which only σ -bonds are found, to identify those components in a complex $\text{K}_{\beta 1,3}$ spectrum which are due to electronic transitions from σ -orbitals and those from π -orbitals. The involvement of $\text{Si } 3p$ orbitals in both σ - and π -bonding to unsaturated ligand (e.g. benzene) is clearly established.

Fig. 4. X-Ray spectra for $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Si}(\text{OH})_2$.

Experimental

X-Ray photoelectron (XP) spectra of inner orbital and valence band were measured using a Vacuum Generators ESCA3 (Mkl) spectrometer operated at pressure of 2×10^{-9} Torr. Powdered samples were mounted by pressing into a gold mesh. Spectra were calibrated with respect to gold line (Au-N6 , 86.4 eV). The XP spectrum of liquid $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$ was obtained by freezing the liquid sample on the end of the probe using liquid nitrogen. X-Ray emission (XE) spectra of silicon compounds were measured on a Philips PW 1410 spectrometer operated at $10^{-2} - 10^{-3}$ Torr. Powdered sample were mounted in a terephthalic acid disc, then inserted into the spectrometer and irradiated with a chromium anode X-ray tube operated at 50 kV and 50 mA. The liquid sample was placed in a cell, covered at one side with $10 \mu\text{m}$ mylar through which the liquid was irradiated. Fine collimation was used in conjunction with EDDT crystal, the overall resolving power $E/\Delta E$ being ca. 800.

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